

INFLUENCE OF VARIOUS ACADEMIC COURSES ON GENERAL SELF-EFFICACY AMONG STUDENTS OF PANJAB UNIVERSITY, CHANDIGARH

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to study the influence of various academic courses (Hindi, Punjabi, Physical education, Education) on general self-efficacy among the students of Panjab University. 220 students were selected as the sample of the study using purposive sampling. Data was collected by General Self-Efficacy questionnaire (Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem, M. 1995). The obtained value at $df(3,216) = 2.60$ was lower than the table value of 2.65, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean scores of general self-efficacy of the four groups. This suggests that engagement in different academic courses only does not influence the general self-efficacy levels.

Key words: *Self-Efficacy, Courses, Academic involvement*

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of self-efficacy was first defined as an individual's belief in their capability to successfully perform tasks required to achieve meaningful goals (Bandura, 1977). Self-efficacy has become one of the most extensively studied constructs in psychology, with applications in almost each field of human behaviour (Bandura, 1997; Maddux, 1995). Importantly, self-efficacy is not about the actual possession of skills but about one's confidence in using those skills effectively. It is also not regarded as a fixed personality trait, meaning that people cannot

be categorized as simply having high or low self-efficacy (Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998). Instead, individuals develop efficacy beliefs in relation to specific tasks and life domains. For instance, a student who trusts their ability to apply academic skills to succeed in school demonstrates high academic self-efficacy (Maddux & Kleiman, 2025). Although often confused with self-esteem, self-efficacy is a different concept. Self-esteem reflects how much value you place on yourself, while self-efficacy refers to confidence in your ability to succeed in specific areas of life. Self-efficacy can influence self-esteem, but only in domains that matter to the individual—for instance, athletic self-efficacy will affect self-esteem only if athletic success is personally important (Maddux & Kleiman, 2025).

Koyuncuoglu (2023) found that engaging in university courses that develop metacognitive skills can lead to enhance the self-efficacy of students. Similarly, Fenning and May (2013) demonstrated that active participation in various courses can strengthen the belief in one's own coping abilities. Ma linauskas (2017) found that focused instructional programs, especially teacher education, boosted general and social self-efficacy, suggesting that experiential learning can lead to confidence improvements. On the other hand, Bong (1997) examined academic self-efficacy across different subjects and found that general self-efficacy (GSE) had only a minimal association with students' actual achievements or confidence in specific courses. He states that excelling in one subject does not always lead to the enhancement of a student's overall belief in their abilities. Jyani & Dudy (2024) conducted a comparative study of vocational and traditional courses in relation to self-efficacy and hope. Findings state that students who enrolled in vocational courses had higher future expectations in comparison to traditional course students. On the other hand, the score of general self-efficacy was found to be non-significant, which means that both groups had the same level of self-efficacy irrespective of the academic environment. This study intends to explore how engagement in different academic environments impact students' confidence in managing tasks and overcoming challenges across different aspects of life.

OBJECTIVE

To assess the general self-efficacy of university students pursuing various courses (Hindi, Education, and Physical Education).

HYPOTHESIS

H₀₁ There is no significant difference in the mean general self-efficacy scores of the groups of students pursuing different academic courses.

TOOL USED

General Self-efficacy scale constructed by Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem, M. (1995).

METHOD AND PROCEDURE

The descriptive method of research was used to conduct the study. The purposive sampling method was used to collect data on self-efficacy from the students of four departments of Punjab University Chandigarh. The sample consisted of 220 students pursuing various courses in the Hindi, Education, Physical education and Punjabi department of the university. A well-established measurement scale constructed by Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem, M. (1995) on General Self-efficacy containing ten items was distributed to the students in Hindi, Education, Physical education and Punjabi department of the university. The identity and responses of the students were kept confidential. The data were collected with the consent of students, and the researcher personally visited the classrooms for the collection of data. One-way ANOVA was performed to compare the means of all four groups with the help of SPSS software.

RESULTS

Table 1

Descriptive Analysis of General Self-Efficacy among the four groups

Std. Error	Std. Deviation	Mean	N	Departments
.59	4.60	32.18	60	Hindi
.59	4.61	30.13	60	Education
.64	4.95	30.56	60	Physical Education
.71	4.53	29.78	40	Punjabi

From Table1, it can be observed that the mean scores of the students from various courses such as Hindi, Education, Physical Education and Punjabi on general self-efficacy are 32.18, 30.13, 30.56 and 29.78 respectively.

Table 2

One way ANOVA summary of the four groups

F	Mean Square	df	Sum of Squares	
2.60	57.30	3	171.90	Between Groups
	22.02	216	4757.62	Within Groups

As Table 2 shows, the obtained F value for df= 3, 216, is 2.60, which is lower than Table Value of 2.65. Hence, it is not significant at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the four groups pursuing various courses in Panjab University Chandigarh do not differ significantly in general self-efficacy. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{01} "There is no significant difference in the mean general self-efficacy scores of the groups of students pursuing different academic courses" is not rejected. It may therefore be said that the students pursuing the four courses in departments of

Hindi, Education, Physical Education and Punjabi do not differ significantly on general self-efficacy.

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to assess the general self-efficacy among students of different academic departments of Panjab University Chandigarh. The objective was to explore whether engagement in varied academic environments such as Hindi, Education, Physical Education and Punjabi influence students' overall belief in their capabilities. The result indicated no significant difference in the mean scores of general self-efficacy among the four groups suggesting that the nature of the course alone does not affect the overall beliefs of the individual.

Yahya et al. (2019) revealed a strong positive relationship between students' engagement in academic-related co-curricular activities and their personality development. It contributes to the idea that continuous participation in structured academic or physical programs helps build confidence in discipline and social skills. These attributes are closely related to the construct of self-efficacy which emphasizes an individual's belief in their ability to perform tasks successfully.

In the context of the present study, the environment of each academic course is different. The students from Hindi department are primarily engaged in the thrust areas like Medieval and Modern Hindi Literature, Indian Poetry. Specialization: Philology, Tradition of Hindi Ram Kavya, Hindi Fiction, Modern Hindi Poetry and Prose etc. which indicates that these students are not involved in any kind of physical training or adventures activities during their course duration. In contrast, the students of physical education department are highly engaged in sports activities and physical training, while the students from the Department of Education are involved in the study of Education for Peace, Values & Sustainable development, Philosophical, Sociological and Psychological foundations of Education, Guidance & Counselling, Educational Technology, Measurement and Evaluation, Social and Economic Context of Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Environmental Education, Educational Administration and Educational Research which means they have a very different classroom environment in comparison of Hindi and Physical Education. On the other hand, the students of Punjabi department study about the History of Punjabi literature, Punjabi criticism, Gurmat and Sufi poetry, Study of Punjabi

story, Punjabi Novel etc. reflecting that the curriculum of their academic course is only related to the literature study of their subject. Hence, the environments of the study areas of each course are different from each other which means the samples from the four groups face different situations and complications in their day-to-day life.

The findings of the present study support the results of Chen, Gully, & Eden (2004). He observed only slight and instable differences in general self-efficacy over different training and academic proposing that course specific confidence and for a theoretical distinction between course-specific self-efficacy and generalized beliefs. This indicates that completing courses might enhance domain-specific efficacy without certainly shaping one's general self-belief. Lindley and Borgen (2002) discovered that general self-efficacy (GSE) showed only average links with academic results across various themes, and its potential to forecast success varied between course types. These findings dispute the idea that succeeding in academic courses naturally enhances overall self-efficacy and it can be said that being involved in various academic courses alone does not affect the level of general self-efficacy.

CONCLUSION

Courses might enhance the domain-specific efficacy but cannot boost the overall beliefs of one's capabilities. Completing a particular course may improve the confidence in that specific field or subject but it cannot automatically enhance the broader sense of generalized self-efficacy.

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